

Study of Some New Mixed Schiff Base Complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) Containing Fused Ring Systems

B. A. JANI, R. K. KOHLI and P. K BHATTACHARYA

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

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A series of mixed ligand complexes of the type MLL' $M=Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$; L =Schiff base derived from 2-acetyl-1-naphthol and L' =Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy acetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiofenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been prepared and characterised on the basis of analytical, magnetic moment and electronic and I.R. spectral studies. Reactions with diamines have been carried out in all above cases. $Cu(II)$ complexes were subjected to alkanol amine reactions also.

MIXED ligand complexes of $Cu(II)$ and $Ni(II)$ involving 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been reported from our laboratory¹⁻⁴. It can be expected that there is a greater possibility of $M-L$ π interaction in complexes of ligands with fused rings. In the present study, mixed Schiff base complexes MLL' have been synthesized, where $M=Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$, $L=2$ -acetyl-1-naphthalaldimine and L' =salicylaldimine, 2-hydroxy acetophenonimine, 2-hydroxy propiophenonimine or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalaldimine(I).

$M=Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$

$R=H, CH_3,$ or C_2H_5

Ring $x=$ benzene or naphthalene

Amine exchange reactions have been carried out on the complexes with diamines and alkanolamines. (I) on treatment with ethylenediamine or 1,2 propylene diamine gave transamination products(II).

In case of $Cu(II)$ complex(I), reaction with ethanolamine or isopropanolamine gave a tridentate ligand complex(III). 2-Acetyl-1-naphthol forms a tridentate ligand complex on condensation with monoalkanol amine and the other moiety (salicylaldimine, 2-hydroxy acetophenonimine or 2-hydroxy propiophenonimine) is knocked out resulting in the

$M=Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$

$R=H, CH_3$ or C_2H_5

$R'=H$ or CH_3

Ring $X=$ benzene or naphthalene

formation of III A, $R=H, 1,2,3$ or $R=CH_3, 1,2,3$ respectively. However, in the case where L and L' are 2-acetyl-1-naphthalaldimine and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalaldimine respectively, the former is knocked out and the latter forms a tridentate complex (III B).

III A

$R=H (1, 2, 3)$

$=CH_3 (1, 2, 3)$

III B
R = H or CH₃

Methods and Material : Salicylaldehyde (BDH), 2-hydroxy acetophenone (B I, Germany), 2-hydroxy propiophenone (Sisco) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) were all of laboratory grade, whereas 2-acetyl-1-naphthol was prepared as under :

α-naphthol (40 g), anhydrous ZnCl₂ (40 g) and 20 ml dry nitrobenzene were taken in 250 ml standard joint flask. To this 24 g of dry acetyl

chloride was added from standard joint funnel while stirring on magnetic stirrer for three hours. The flask was then corked and was allowed to stand 48 hours at room temperature. A mixture of two isomers viz. 1-acetyl-4-naphthol and 2-acetyl 1-naphthol was obtained. The latter was removed by dissolving in benzene, the former being practically insoluble. This was recrystallized from alcohol and analysed.

Complexes I, II and III were synthesized as detailed earlier⁴. Analyses, TLC, molar conductance, magnetic and spectral studies required for characterization of these complexes have been carried out as detailed earlier¹⁻⁴. Relevant data have been presented in the table.

Results and Discussion

The TLC and the analysis of the mixed Schiff base complexes indicate that they are single compounds and have structures I, II and III.

TABLE—ANALYTICAL DATA, ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BAND AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS

Sl. No.	Complex*	Metal%		Nitrogen%		λ _{max}	μ _{eff}
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found		
1.	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(I ; R=H)	17.28	17.18	7.61	7.81	560	1.88
2.	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(I ; R=H)	16.18	16.10	7.71	7.57	550	1.40
3.	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(I ; R=OH ₂)	16.66	16.52	7.34	7.14	565	1.76
4.	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(I ; R=OH ₂)	15.88	15.72	7.43	6.94	550	Diamagnetic
5.	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(I ; R=C ₂ H ₅)	16.07	16.15	7.08	7.16	555	1.68
6.	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(I ; R=C ₂ H ₅)	15.02	15.42	7.17	6.77	560	Diamagnetic
7.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(I)	15.21	15.34	6.70	6.50	555	1.81
8.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II)	14.22	14.10	6.78	6.88	540	1.23
9.	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(II ; R=R'=H)	16.14	15.98	7.11	7.02	555	1.90
10.	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II ; R=R'=H)	15.10	15.18	7.20	6.82	555	Partially paramagnetic
11.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(II ; R=H, R'=CH ₃)	15.59	15.70	6.87	6.58	570	1.84
12.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II ; R=H, R'=CH ₃)	14.57	14.40	6.95	6.60	540	Partially paramagnetic
13.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(II ; R=CH ₃ ; R'=H)	15.60	15.84	6.87	7.01	550	1.92
14.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II ; R=CH ₃ ; R'=H)	14.57	14.41	6.95	6.86	555	Partially paramagnetic
15.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(II ; R=OH ₂ ; R'=OH ₂)	15.08	14.66	6.64	6.37	545	1.88
16.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II, R=CH ₃ ; R'=OH ₂)	14.09	14.48	6.72	7.06	555	Diamagnetic
17.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(II ; R=C ₂ H ₅ ; R'=H)	15.08	15.14	6.64	6.66	545	1.78
18.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II ; R=C ₂ H ₅ ; R'=CH ₃)	14.09	14.25	6.72	6.83	550	Diamagnetic
19.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(II ; R=C ₂ H ₅ ; R'=H)	14.60	15.02	6.43	5.89	550	1.95
20.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II ; R=C ₂ H ₅ ; R'=CH ₃)	13.63	13.93	6.50	6.89	550	Diamagnetic
21.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(II ; R=H)	14.32	14.21	6.31	6.05	560	1.85
22.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II ; R=CH ₃)	13.38	13.14	6.98	6.54	550	Partially paramagnetic
23.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cu(II ; R=OH ₂)	13.88	13.70	6.11	6.57	540	1.80
24.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Ni(II ; R=OH ₂)	12.96	13.03	6.18	6.33	540	Partially paramagnetic
25.	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCu(IIIA ; R=H, 1)	20.60	20.40	4.53	4.38	610	1.72
26.	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ NCu(IIIA ; R=CH ₃ , 1)	19.71	19.89	4.33	4.60	625	1.88
27.	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCu(IIIA ; R=H, 2)	20.60	20.45	4.53	4.97	620	1.82
28.	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ NCu(IIIA ; R=CH ₃ , 2)	19.71	19.82	4.33	4.68	620	1.77
29.	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCu(IIIA ; R=H, 3)	20.60	20.51	4.53	4.09	625	1.96
30.	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ NCu(IIIA ; R=CH ₃ , 3)	19.71	19.94	4.33	4.82	615	1.86
31.	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCu(IIIB ; R=H)	21.57	21.25	4.75	4.85	630	1.72
32.	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ NCu(IIIB ; R=CH ₃)	20.60	20.50	4.53	4.38	620	1.75

* Entries inside the brackets refer to structural formulae.

Cu(II) complexes are all paramagnetic corresponding to one unpaired electron. In the spectra of the complexes a broad band is obtained in the visible range. This corresponds to the combination of three close energy bands. The λ_{\max} can be approximately equated with $10 Dq$. It is observed that in case of a mixed Schiff base complex containing 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalimine and 2-acetyl-1-naphtholimine λ_{\max} is lowest, corresponding to highest $10Dq$. This is because in such complexes metal to ligand π bonding is maximum due to the possibility of the delocalization of electrons over two pairs of fused rings. This leads to the formation of strong metal-nitrogen bond.

On reaction of (I) with diamines, amine-exchange takes place leading to the formation of complexes of new Schiff bases with the diamine condensed to two different carbonyl groups at the two ends. There is disappearance of $-NH$ stretching in the I.R. spectrum. This accounts for complete exchange of ammonia by the diamine. Further, extinction coefficients of the visible spectral bands in the diamine Schiff base complexes(II) become higher and indicate *cis* structure with both $>C=N$ groups on the same side, leading to the lowering of symmetry.

The reaction of alkanol amine on mixed Schiff base complex is also interesting as discussed earlier⁶. This establishes the mixed ligand nature of the complexes. The alkanol amine reacts with one carbonyl compound forming tridentate Schiff base complex and the other one is removed. The one that is removed is supposed to have less tendency to form Schiff base complex. On the basis of such studies the order of the hydroxy

carbonyl compounds to form the Schiff base was suggested⁶. This order can be further extended on the basis of present studies as 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde $>$ 2-acetyl-1-naphthol $>$ salicylaldehyde $>$ 2-hydroxy acetophenone $>$ 2-hydroxy propiophenone.

In case of Ni(II), square planar complexes are expected to be diamagnetic. However, some Ni(II) complexes exhibit partial paramagnetism due to polymerization by coordinating through oxygen atom to the axial positions of Ni(II) in the other complex molecule⁶⁻⁷-leading to distorted octahedral-structure. In solution, however, the polymerization breaks and a shoulder is obtained at ~ 550 nm.

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